

Modelling Worker's Perspective to the use of Automated System

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Abstract

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Contrarily to the existing surveys, this study is dedicated to operations management problems (focusing on the applications and features) for human and machine/robot collaborative systems in manufacturing. The method adopted is divided into two types of interactions between human and automated components in manufacturing and assembly systems: dual resource constrained (DRC) and human-robot collaboration (HRC) optimization problems. Different characteristics of the workforce and machines/robots such as heterogeneity, homogeneity, ergonomics, and flexibility are introduced. Finally, the paper identifies the optimization challenges and problems for hybrid systems. The existing literature on HRC focuses mainly on the robotic point of view and not on the operations management and optimization aspects. Therefore, the future research directions include the design of models and methods to optimize HRC systems in terms of ergonomics and safety. In addition, studying flexibility and configurability in hybrid systems is one of the main research avenues for future perspective.

Keywords: human-robot collaboration, dual resource constrained, Agent-based modeling, Simulation, Worker.

1 Introduction

Automation of manufacturing systems is an ongoing trend in the industrial sector. At the same time, for many industries, the transition to a fully automated remains an insurmountable challenge to the model. However, Industry 4.0 fosters the adoption of collaborative robots (cobots). Indeed, the recent advances in artificial intelligence and sensor devices gave rise to this new type of robot able to collaborate with humans and to perform a wide variety of tasks [20, 6, 1].

These cobots (e.g., dual-arm assembly robots) lead to a manufacturing system, where humans and robots work side by side. Such a system is called a human/robot collaborative (HRC) system. Several studies report the benefits of HRC systems in terms of product quality, ergonomics, safety, and flexibility [11, 2] Nevertheless, these robots are expensive, and their introduction in manufacturing systems requires significant effort.

From mathematical and computer modeling perspectives, the robot's characteristics appear similar to those of human operators, and this could explain the lack of operations management literature on HRC systems. In other words, both humans and robots are considered resources with a specific set of skills.

However, robots and humans have different characteristics [17, 14, 3] Robots possess high speed, accuracy, tirelessness, and force, but they are quite expensive. On the other hand, human workers are intelligent, creative, flexible, and able to work with different tools in different situations. These different characteristics lead to the definition of specific operations management problems for HRC systems, such as the design of hybrid workstations combining efficiently the human and robot skills, scheduling problems that account for ergonomics, the design of re-configurable HRC systems where workers and cobots move from one station to another to re-balance the line when needed. The design of flexible or re-configurable automated systems is a hard task. The development of computer numerical control (CNC) machines helped to tackle this challenge with flexible automation in the manufacturing systems (e.g. FMSs). The recent advances in robotics led to the creation of machines able to process a large variety of tasks, and these new robots will further extend the flexibility of automated manufacturing systems. Nevertheless, human workers remain the most flexible component of a manufacturing system. In the mass customization area, manufacturing systems must rely on humans to attain the desired flexibility level [5, 6]. The adoption of robots in manufacturing systems creates new operations management challenges. For instance, robots and workers have different capacities, and this affects the allocation of the resources in the system and the assignment of tasks to the workforce/robots. Besides, ergonomics and risk assessments are of critical importance in HRC manufacturing systems. Consequently, the model to design, plan, and schedule the tasks must account for ergonomics and safety constraints. Finally, hybrid human-robot systems can be very flexible and re-configurable if designed appropriately. The next section presents how the existing literature accounts for these characteristics. [20, 5].

1.1 Problem of the statement

Automation challenges are faced due to inefficient processes, the trends around automation have accelerated, also the technology could erode workers bargaining power and the poor adoption in choosing the wrong solution adoption of a common thread connecting many organizations is the belief that workflow management software will automatically fix bad and inefficient. There is a need to combat the negative effect of this automated system and workers often need to maintain the relevant skills and need new complex skills to operate this technology. The research aims to examine how substituting technol-

ogy, enables workers to perform a specific task.

1.2 Agent-based modeling

ABM is a simulation method aimed at analyzing a complex social system by using virtual agents to imitate the behaviors and interactions of individuals in the system. ABM regards the outcome as an emergent property of individual agent behaviors and interactions among agents. This bottom-up method makes ABM more appropriate to develop inherently nonlinear [17, 7]. Models than traditional equation-based modeling methods, Besides ABM can be used as an experimental method to test what-if scenarios and illustrate the effectiveness of management strategies study production problems [1] He further suggests that the effects of workers' social learning on absenteeism and concluded that cultivating a good culture was more effective than regulating individuals for worker attendance control. [20, 8] proposed the simulation of the evolution of collaboration in temporary project teams and indicated that the system was less efficient when more efforts were needed to form relationships. Prior research has also used the ABM method to address challenges in construction supply chain construction operations with traffic congestion, and construction dispute resolution construction management education. [2, 9] Besides, several attempts have been made to utilize ABM to study safety issues in the construction industry but none of them involve interactions between workers and management teams used ABM to explore the relationships between employer attitudes and worker behaviors towards production and reward goals.[11, 10] tried to utilize ABM to interpret why the construction accident rate only decreased by half in the past two decades in Hong Kong when safety investment had increased three times.

1.2.1 Model Components

In general, an agent-based model is structured by three elements:

- i A set of agents
- ii interactions between agents
- iii interactions between agents and their environment

The model uses the role behaviors of each management role, a survey was carried out to investigate the typical management behaviors related to the workers' safety performance. The rules that govern the interactions between worker agents and management agents were defined in the model construction phase based on these findings. Finally, a typical unsafe worker behavior was modeled and used to simulate the interactions between the environment and agents. This unsafe behavior was repeatedly observed during the surveys and had long been criticized as the major cause of various Jobsite accidents to

investigate the importance of different roles on safety, as perceived by all workers and management. [3, 14].

1.2.2 Interaction between the agents and the environment

When studying safety issues, the interactions between the site environment and the personnel refers to the behavior of personnel when they encounter potential hazards on sites. They can take safe actions to avoid accidents or risky ones for other purposes putting themselves in danger. The automated system has several advantages for the industry, such as improved productivity, product quality and profitability, improved hygiene and safety, and worker safety [7, 11]. Moreover, the use of an automated system help to reduce injuries, and decrease the cost of labour [2, 13]. Automation is technology-related to applying mechanical, electronic, and computer-based systems to operate and control production. The automation technology included; [8, 15].

- 1 Automatic machine tools to process parts
- 2 Automatic assembly machines
- 3 Industrial robots
- 4 Automated material handling and storage system
- 5 Automated inspection system for quality control
- 6 Feedback control and computer process control
- 7 The computer system for planning, data collection, and decision making to support manufacturing facilities.

1.2.3 Worker safety

The central concept of worker safety is to isolate automated systems from human work. The mixed working environment is highlighted for improvement in the efficiency of industrial robots [10, 20]. However, the concept has a technical execution point of view. The new images, including recording current activities and considering the context and applicable situation, access the risk potential to which a worker could be exposed because of the robot's movement [13, 12].

D.Characteristics of workforce and machine/robot
Industrial components (e.g., workforce, machines, and robots) possess different skills, and thus they can perform different tasks, this led to the classification of workforce assignment problems into two categories: homogeneous workers or heterogeneous workers. In a manufacturing system with homogeneous workers, all workers are the same with respect to their skills, physical abilities, labor costs, or any other characteristics. Consequently, each worker can perform all the tasks. On the contrary, in a system with a heterogeneous workforce, workers have different skills or skill levels, which creates resource-task

Figure 1: Workforce Human and robots interaction

assignment restrictions. Typically, in workforce planning problems with heterogeneous resources, each operator is associated with a skill set and an assignment is feasible if the assigned task is covered by the operator's skill. These skill-sets may be identical, non-identical, or in some cases overlapping from one resource to another. [5, 16]. This section presents the main elements to consider when managing a manufacturing system with humans and robots. First, the inefficient system must carefully manage and combine the skills of both humans and robots. Second, the introduction of cobots can enhance the ergonomics of the systems. For instance, the cobot can perform or assist the workers to perform painful or dangerous tasks. However, in novel HRC systems, robots and workers operate.

2 Literature Review

[5, 17] Proposed a system that integrates humans into intelligent manufacturing systems and raises awareness of the risks linked to removing humans from the control loop. An assistance system (AS) has been designed to help humans when they have to supervise and control an artificial self-organizing manufacturing control system. The assistance system provides system context to a human using an emulator. [20, 19] suggested considering the use of knowledge representation for decision making at runtime in manufacturing. Semantic models are utilized as knowledge repositories of CPS, and ontologies are employed by the service orchestrators for planning and ordering the execution operations with all available resources, including those about human operations. A human performance assessment approach is used in [8, 18] to predict human behavior during Human-CPS interaction based on the input data collected from pilots' responses in a flight simulator.

Several sets of testing with real pilots in the different stages of training were performed to collect the measurements, and data histograms are created to identify, the

item distribution of the identified parameters. assembly. Before starting the task, the human teaches the robot the specific of the task using natural language instructions. The collaborative task is dynamically handled by the human and the robot, and the robot acts by learning from human demonstrations. Combining the rewards and demonstration features together, the robot is able to extract an optimal goal action for new tasks. [11, 4] proposed a performance metrics method is presented to improve the effectiveness of the tiny embedded manufacturing systems. A production goal is decomposed into hierarchical sub-goals with the aim of limiting the costs and reducing complexity. The overall throughput effectiveness (OTE) of a parent system is obtained from the OTEs of its children in a hierarchical tree. This way, the improvement actions are distributed across the CPS. With the use of declarative programming, these actions remain understandable both by humans and automated actors.

[13, 21] the authors present two implementations of HiTL-CPS cognitive capability concepts. The first implementation deals with machine learning and condition monitoring capabilities, and the second one enhances human capabilities with visual analytics. The first case involves human actors for enhancing machine learning capabilities to integrate CPS with human knowledge. The second case provides visual analytics to human monitoring to augment human capabilities for decision-making tasks. the authors use an agent that provides adaptability to robotic operators. The aim is to minimize the impact of human performance variation via a reinforcement learning algorithm. This algorithm generates instructions to adjust the operational parameters of the robot in a simulated smart factory environment. The simulation model contains parameters to represent several different operations and human actors. The agent learns the temporal patterns of the workers over these parameters to overcome performance disparity and minimize operator idle time.[18] proposed a Model and solution approaches dedicated to human-machine systems. [9, 22] also suggested that focusing on the human-machine interface models should be implemented.[7, 4] Propose to Design applications and communication types between partners in HRC systems.

[8, 19] Suggested that Applications of HRC systems in education, industry, entertainment, health, and military. [18, 17] design Human-robot task planning, scheduling, and coordination in manufacturing systems (robotic point of view). [16] Design of a safe HRC system in an intelligent manufacturing environment. [8] Applications and classification of HRC assembly systems. [9] Various methods to improve safety in HRC systems. [1]. Different technologies and algorithms for gesture recognition as an interface between humans and robots in HRC systems.[3] Challenges and applications of HRC in manufacturing systems. [10] Intermediate interfaces, robots'

interaction modalities, and stability in HRC systems. [6] Different types of communication between humans and robots in HRC systems. [7]. Different types of interaction between humans and robots in HRC systems.

Deep learning methods that incorporate CNNs have been demonstrated to be effective for computer vision and pattern recognition [13] developed the LeNet-5 (a CNN model), which recognizes handwritten numbers, based on a dataset created by the Mixed National Institute of Standards and Technology. CNN models can effectively and automatically recognize features from static images by stacking multiple convolutions and pooling layers. [8, 21] was the first to achieve substantially high levels of image classification accuracy at the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (LSVRC) by training a deep CNN. Since the inception of deep CNN, almost all the effective algorithms used for image classification, object recognition, and visual tracking that have been developed are based on this fundamental work. proposed an online visual tracking algorithm by learning a discriminate saliency map using a CNN, which provided superior results compared to other state-of-the-art tracking algorithms (e.g. discrete Fourier transform (DSK), local sparse and K-selection (LSK), and circulant structure of tracking-by-detection with kernels (CSK) [18, 22].

3 Method

To attain the study goal and objectives, a survey was administered to field engineers with different work titles, such as project manager, project engineer, safety engineer, and other engineering personnel. The sample consists of 10 construction management personnel from Nigeria. More than 50 questions were asked in the survey. However, only certain questions are used in the current study. In addition to questions about respondent demographics, other questions were stated to extract information about the opportunities and shortcomings of using an automated system. Open-ended questions were used to allow the respondent a wider range of responses. The open-ended questions were complemented with a mix of closed-ended questions. However, the closed-ended questions were developed in such a way that the respondent could add more than the provided choices. Utilizing both types of questions was intended to reduce the bias that could result from determining options in the questionnaire.

The survey provides an opportunity to gain a better understanding of construction worker safety from an engineer's perspective. A convenience sample is used for the study as it is difficult to utilize an entirely random sampling process in the construction industry. As a result, we need to evaluate the validity and reliability of the survey to ensure confidence in the results. Institutional Review Board approval was gained for the questionnaire before its distribution as the survey targets human sub-

jects. The online secure research suite Qualtrics was used to distribute the survey and collect the responses. The first step consisted of sending the survey to the chosen sample of engineers by email, and then the participants responded using the Qualtrics website. A condition was set for each Qualtrics survey link attached to the email so that only one response could be gathered from the link. The results section is divided into three subsections for ease in presenting and interpreting the results. The first subsection presents the demographic information of the respondents. The second subsection describes the survey responses related to some shortcomings of using the automated system from the perspective of field engineers. Lastly, the third subsection provides descriptive statistics about modeling opportunities in construction and automated system impact on workers' safety. Also, an econometric modeling technique was applied in this to show variables that are statistically linked to the impact of using automated systems on the enhancement of construction safety.

3.1 Analysis Using Econometric Model

The statistical impact in determining if BIM improves safety, an econometric modeling technique was applied to utilize the survey results. Responses from the management personnel were used to shed light on the factors that lead to construction personnel thinking that BIM increases safety. In doing so, the binary logistic regression modeling framework was utilized due to having only two possible outcomes 1 if BIM increases safety and 0 otherwise. This modeling framework has been utilized and presented in transportation safety literature [11, 15], yet applying this econometric technique with regard to construction safety is scarce. With that in mind, to determine the probability that the outcome takes the value 1 (e.g., BIM increases safety), the following binary logit form applies [15].

$$PS = e^2\beta + e\beta \quad (1)$$

where

$$\beta e = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_k \quad (2)$$

where PS is the probability that construction personnel believe BIM increases safety, β are the estimated parameters and X are the explanatory variables used to determine the outcome probability. For this analysis, the estimated parameters are simply the coefficient outputs, βe , provided by the modeling framework. The explanatory variables used for this analysis are variables selected based on the responses from the survey. For example, workers who have 5 to 10 years of experience in the construction industry are used as an explanatory variable to determine if workers with such experience believe that the use of an automated system improves safety. Upon fitting several models, the best fit binary logit model was

obtained based on the statistical significance of each variable. Each explanatory variable accounted for at least 10% of the total observations and descriptive statistics of significant variables are shown in Table 1

The methodology can be used by construction managers and planners, responsible for preparing and implementing the schedule, the use of the methodology should ensure that these plans are based on correct assumptions regarding the workspaces which will reflect actual requirements. This will in turn reduce workers' risks and increase the probability of achieving the planned productivity targets. To ensure that users will be willing to adopt the approach in practice, the methodology is user-friendly and easy to apply.

3.2 Building Information Modelling Shortcomings

It is assumed that all technology solutions come with shortcomings, and the use of building information modeling is one of these solutions. The shortcomings might arise from the use of the technology itself, the conditions of the work environment in which the technology is used, or other factors. Different drawbacks of using BIM should be considered from the engineer's perspective. The most cited shortcomings are its lack of suitability for all projects and an absence of a need for BIM on all projects. Linking this result with the high cost of owning and operating the technology [14] makes sense logically as most general contractors place a high priority on the profits of their work (also, the highest percentage of the respondents were general contractor employees). In addition, required training and its associated costs are viewed by a large percentage of respondents (48%) as a shortcoming that impacts the tendency to adopt the technology.

Furthermore, the resistance of people within the organization(s) is considered another shortcoming which was chosen by 42% of respondents. The respondents identified other shortcomings as well; the entire list is shown in Figure 1. The respondents provided suggestions for ways to improve and expand the use of BIM in the construction industry. Among these suggestions was educating stakeholders about the benefits and impact of using the technology. This can be accomplished by conducting workshops from the technology manufacturer and/or the governmental entities that support the idea.

The transition of an organization to adopt a new practice or technology in the workplace is not easy due to several factors and requires planning. The respondents, however, think that the transition to a BIM environment for projects can be done safely and smoothly. Fifty-eight percent of the respondents agreed with this perspective, while 17% were unsure of the transition. On the other hand, 25% of the respondents think that it is not safe to transition to a BIM environment. Again, this result

Table 1: Descriptive statistics and descriptions of significant variables.

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Experience in Construction Industry (1 if 5 to 10 Years, 0 Otherwise)	0.245	0.434
BIM Ease Communication Among Project Parties	0.653	0.481
Object Delivery Method Affect Which Technology is Used	0.796	0.407
Job Title (1 if Project Manager, 0 Otherwise)	0.286	0.456
Age (1 if Less Than 30 Years, 0 Otherwise)	0.367	0.487
Projects	0.388	0.49

Figure 2: Shortcomings of the use of the automated system by the construction Worker

Figure 3: Responses regarding using BIM in every firm in the construction market

might be due to the resistance that industry and/or organizational culture has created in their minds. One of the most important aspects of the difficulty of transitioning to a BIM environment might be the interpretation of the BIM model. Those who support the transition and those who were unsure of the transition (81% of the respondents) indicated that BIM models are easy to interpret. Only 19% percent of the respondents were unsure if it is easy to interpret BIM models and no respondents think it is difficult. This result supports the idea of extending his result requires additional investigation to gain a clearer and more comprehensive understanding of the responses. Figure 2 shows that the highest percentage of respondents think the use of BIM should depend on the needs of the firm the use of BIM and the need to change the culture of resistance in the construction industry. The above result for those who are not in favor of using BIM in all firms might also indicate that implementing the procedures and products of BIM requires more

Figure 4: Impact of BIM in discovering design errors.

training and testing. This issue was also assessed in the questionnaire. In fact, 70% of the respondents are divided equally between being accepting or unsure about whether BIM products should receive more testing and if more training is needed. Regarding the time needed for a firm to implement this technology throughout the firm, most, respondents (55%) stated that a 1 to 3-year period is needed. This time frame suggestion is acceptable as the transition period to apply the technology in a limited range after a firm has adopted a BIM product (e.g., first for one project), then extend the use to additional projects and train people, falls within the 1 to 3 year period specified by the respondents.

Thirty-two percent of the respondents believe that more than three years is required for a firm to use BIM smoothly in their work. Regarding safety opportunities, respondents state that BIM is beneficial in discovering errors in the design earlier. Ninety-seven percent agreed that this opportunity is offered by BIM, as shown in Figure 4. This high level of the agreement indicates that both field and management engineers may have experienced positive results with respect to safety from implementing BIM. The essence of this benefit might be magnified if connected with other safety and health improvement concepts.

To ensure that the respondents were consistent with their answers, the questionnaire included a direct question regarding personnel construction safety and whether safety performance improves, as a result of reducing risk, when BIM is used. Forty-nine percent of the respondents believe safety improves when using BIM and 41% were unsure of its impact, as shown in Figure 4. A small percentage of respondents (11%) believe safety is not enhanced with the use of BIM. In fact, the portion of the 40% of respondents who indicated that they were unsure might support the statement that safety improves after using

Figure 5: Impact of automated system uses on a safety level.

the technology if the respondents knew more about the technology.

Construction safety is perceived to improve with the adoption of the technologies. Cost improvement, and reduced omissions and change orders are examples of benefits when using BIM [14]. Further, the uncertainty in their responses might be attributed to not having perceived the indirect impact of design errors on safety since their focus is on discovering errors only as shown in Figure 4. It is sometimes the case that there is still uncertainty about the direct and indirect causes of safety issues. Explaining the issue of the direct and indirect impacts of design errors on safety may lead to more positive responses to the question about whether BIM.

The survey discloses that using BIM may help with the project delivery method, and choosing whether to use the technology is impacted by the delivery method itself. Regarding the project delivery method that their firms use traditionally with projects that adopt BIM, the engineers stated that design-build is the most commonly used delivery method (52% of respondents). Design-bid-build and CM-at-risk were the second choices, each with 42% of the respondents, while other methods received a 30% response rate. In fact, this result is consistent with the literature that states that the design-build delivery method is the most frequently used delivery method for complex projects [?]. Design-build and the traditional design-bid-build method comprise a greater share of the construction contracting methods used in practice. Moreover, 72% of the respondents think that the choice of which technology to use on a project is affected by the delivery method. This result requires further research to show why a specific project delivery method is preferred over others with regard to using BIM.

4 Result Discussion

Our survey shows a growing amount of research on HRC systems in the last few years. This interest is related to the large benefits of HRC systems for manufacturers, such as ergonomics, safety, productivity, and flexibility. Different aspects of HRC systems draw particular attention of research communities: robotics, artificial intelligence, communication, software architecture. At

the same time, operations management literature on HRC systems remains scarce and the scope of studied issues is small. For instance, most studies on scheduling for HRC systems seek to minimize the make span, whereas other criteria are rarely considered. Three research directions in operations management regarding HRC systems are identified. The first research direction concerns the extension of DRC problem to account for different cobot interaction modes. This extension includes the definition of manual, automated, and hybrid tasks. Humans perform manual tasks, cobots perform automated tasks, and hybrid tasks require both human and cobot at the same time. These different task types create complex precedence constraints. The inclusion of HRC features into a DRC scheduling problem would lead to the creation of hybrid workstations with the required skill sets. HRC systems are composed of stations with a wide range of skills, and the design of the right station requires the use of advanced optimization approaches. These approaches can be designed based on the DRC literature. The second research avenue suggests including ergonomic constraints in DRC problems. As ergonomics improvement is a major motivation for the introduction of cobots, there is a considerable literature on ergonomics for HRC systems. On the contrary, very few studies exist on ergonomics in DRC problem [20]. However, a careful assignment of tasks to workstations can improve the ergonomics in such systems. With regard to the first research direction, ergonomics corresponds to manual and hybrid stations, mostly. This could be seen as a constraint, especially, when the types of stations are decision variables. Moreover, the third research perspective calls for deeper study of reconfigurability issue of HRC systems.

The systems are usually characterized by a high level of flexibility and reconfigurability. However, it comes at a cost. The design of HRC systems with the right level of flexibility requires advanced optimization methods. The reconfigurability issues of HRC systems. Since robots are expensive, reconfigurability of the system may decrease the cost, because mobile robots and workers can move among stations instead of adding a new robot. Furthermore, variety of collaborative robots' applications like picking and placing, screw driving, inspection, assembly tasks, in addition to their quick and easy set-up, and mobility [11] make their use in reconfigurable manufacturing systems very attractive. Beside collaborative robots, workforce planning would be also interesting as a factor of reconfigurability for HRC systems, [8] Thus, there is a need to develop design methods aiming to enhance the system's reconfigurability. Such methods can leverage on the assembly line balancing literature, and may include stochastic or robust optimization techniques to account for different product sequences, changes in customer demands, and other uncertainties.

In all these research directions, further studies might be

done by defining new optimization functions and/or solution techniques. For example, a function for trading off between either the number of fully manual, automated, and hybrid stations or the number of resources (workforce and robots) in these stations. On the other hand, integrating technologies used in HRC systems with optimization methods creates certain some challenges in terms of operation management techniques. The development of exact methods and/or heuristics should take into account the specificity of proposed technologies or features in HRC systems and may be inspired from (combined with) some techniques used in the control theory.

5 Conclusion

Performing a huge variety of tasks in manufacturing systems requires different types of resources. On the other hand, the reduction of product lifecycles, frequently changing demand and enhanced customization urge industrial companies to employ manufacturing systems with a high level of flexibility and reconfigurability. There exist a huge body of literature on flexibility, system reconfiguration and machine tools reconfiguration. The present paper focuses on the challenges of the interaction between humans and machines/collaborative robots in order to discover potential contributions of operations management methods aimed to improve hybrid systems. The interaction between humans and machines/collaborative robots appears in two manufacturing system types: dual resource constrained system (workers use machines/robots) and human-robot collaboration system (workers and robots collaborate). In the beginning, the main characteristics of human-machine/robot (hybrid) manufacturing systems such as heterogeneity, homogeneity, ergonomics, safety, and flexibility are given. Then, optimization models in terms of design, scheduling, resource planning, and assignment in DRC systems are mentioned.

A summary of studies on HRC systems, making emphasis on the related challenges is provided as well. Finally, a short discussion on the main points of the proposed survey and future research avenues are proposed. According to our survey, reconfigurability is one of the interesting challenges of human-robot systems which has not been sufficiently taken into account in the literature. In addition to the reconfigurability, there are other challenges such as ergonomics, safety, time, flexibility, and productivity. The results confirm the potential of agent-based modeling as an effective approach for analyzing the characteristics and patterns of construction safety behaviors and assessing safety management strategies. The results also reveal the following findings:

- safety training and inspections should be performed at a regular frequency in order to maintain safety performance at a stable high level;
- it is of significant importance for management teams

to emphasize and cultivate the leadership role among supervisors;

- senior managers should be regularly involved in safety activities so that entire project teams can be influenced to behave more safely
- senior managers should not only be able to convey a clear safety goal to subordinates but also be truly concern on and supportive to the achievement of that goal.

Admittedly, the proposed model bears several limitations that can be further addressed in future research. First, the values of a few variables and the formulas of interaction rules used in the model were exemplary. They could be tuned based on empirical evidence for studying specific construction projects. Second, the working environment and tasks modeled were based on example cases and did not necessarily represent all possible situations. Future research can introduce various simulated environments with added complexities to deepen the understanding of construction safety-related behaviors and facilitate the design of safety management strategies practice.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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